

**BIOREMEDIATION OF CONTAMINATED SOILS USING TALL
PLANTS**

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Abstract: Central Kyzylkum is an area of industrial importance, rich in nonferrous and rare-earth metals. The study of the biogeotechnological characteristics of plants in a given region is important for the bioremediation of industrial zones

Key words: industrial zone, phytoextraction, bioremediation, heavy metals, introduced plants, xenobiotics, hyperaccumulation, phytoremediation. In the natural environment, the violation of ecological balance poses a whole series of global problems for mankind. Pollution of the atmosphere, soil, water and food by radioactive substances is not only a threat to living organisms, but also it threatens their future. Of

great importance is the reduction in the biosphere of excessive migration of ecotoxicants, that is, radioactive elements, as well as the prevention along with existing problems of modern environmental problems. The development in the twenty-first century of a large number of enterprises in the mining and metallurgical industry and the use of their industries led to a violation of the general ecological balance of our planet. The periodic circulation of substances in the biosphere causes heavy metals to enter the human body and other living creatures [1]. According to Dutch ecologists, in modern ecotoxicology, the degree of danger of heavy metals and metalloids found in the soil is given in the following order: Se > Tl > Sb > Cd > V > Hg > Ni > Cu > Cr > As > Ba [2].

Not all life-threatening elements found in contaminated soils are well understood. For example, if a lot of research has been done with metals such as Cu, Zn, Pb, Ni, Cd, Cr, As, Mn, Co, Hg, Se, the remaining more than 40 elements have been studied very little. But among them there are such elements, very dangerous for human life, like Ba, V, U, Yb, Ce [2].

To date, the following main tasks have been identified in the study of heavy metals and metalloids found in the soil: 1) the study of metals found in agricultural soils; 2) the use, as fertilizers for plants, of the biological capabilities of metal and phosphorus bodies of water found in mud; 3) the chemical nature of metals in the composition of the soil [3]. Our study is carried out as a part of the study of the biotechnological properties of plants distributed on the liberated lands of the industrial enterprises of Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant, located on the territory of the Central Kizilkum and having important strategic importance for the economy of our country, research and observation work in this territory has been carried out since March 2017. In order to study the biotechnological properties of plants growing on the territory of the Central Kizilkum, the next observation and research work was carried out in September-October 2018 on a landscape with coordinates 40.03' north latitude and 60.00' east longitude. In the course of the experiments, the objects of study were

more than 20 species of plants and the soil of the territory of their growth. To establish the presence of heavy metals in the plants, biomass was collected during the flowering phase, that is, during their high physiological activity. On the landscape of the Central Kizilkum with coordinates 40,031° north latitude and 60,000° east longitude, spread of such plants as *Halimolobos villosa* et. Kar, *Chenopodium glaucum* L. Sp, *Artemisia diffusa*, *Alhagi pseudalhagi* (Bieb) Desv, *Astragalus* sp, *Carex physodes* M.B., *Ferula foetida* (Bge.) Rgl., *Kochia prostrata* (L) Schrad, *Acanthophyllum albidum* Shiski, *Tulipa lechmanniana* Mersk. and *Irissongarcis* observed. Also, in the course of studies of plant and soil samples of the above territory, the following results were obtained. Laboratory analysis of the study was carried out in the laboratory "Ecology and Biotechnology" of the Center for Scientific Research at INP AN Ruz. neutron activation analysis method. Analysis of the samples was carried out with respect to the elements Sm, U, Ce, Tb, Th. In the study of soil samples of the object of study in the soil, the presence of heavy radioactive metals in it was found in the following amounts: Sm - 4.8 mcg/g., U - 4.1 mcg / g., Ce - 56 mcg / g., Tb - 0.78 mcg / g. and Th, 7.4 mcg / g. When analyzing the establishment of some plants found in the environment of this soil in the biomass, the following results were obtained. (table 1).

table 1

Sample No./El.	Sm	U	Ce	Tb	Th
the soil	4,8	4,1	56	0,78	7,4
<i>H.villosa</i>	0,0843	0,216	1,11	0,0155	0,165
<i>Ch.glaucum</i>	0,317	1,4	3,92	0,0641	0,65
<i>A.diffusa</i>	0,148	0,161	1,83	0,0209	0,315
<i>A.pseudalhagi</i>	0,932	0,851	11,3	0,133	1,92
<i>Astragalus</i>	1	0,944	11,8	0,153	2,15
<i>C.physodes</i>	4,06	4,16	51,8	0,554	8,04
<i>F.foetida</i>	0,422	0,836	18,8	0,223	3,24
<i>K.prostrata</i>	4,25	2,71	48,9	0,633	7,9
<i>A. albidum</i>	0,74	0,69	8,8	0,092	1,2
<i>T. lechmanniana</i>	0,43	8,9	4,3	0,046	0,49
<i>I.songarica</i>	0,042	0,12	0,55	0,0066	0,090

The table shows that the amount of Sm element in the composition of the K. prostrataplant is 4.25 mcg / g. and the amount of the Sm element in the composition of the C.physodesplant is 4.06 mcg / g, that is, the amount is close to the amount of this element in the soil, and vice versa the amount of this element in the H.villosaplant is 0.0843 mcg / g, in the Ch.glaucumplant it is 0.317 mcg / g, in the A.diffusaplant it is 0.148 mcg / g, in the A.pseudalhagiplant it is 0.932 mcg / g, in the Astragalusplant it is 1 mcg / g, in the plant F.foetida- 0.422 mcg / g, in A.albidum- 0.74 mcg / g, in T.lechmanniana- 0.43 mcg / g and in I.songarica-0.042 mcg / g. It was found that the amount of U element in the composition of the plant T. lechmanniana (8.9 mcg / g) relative to the amount of element in the soil is 2.2 times higher and in the biomass of the plant C.physodes (4.16 mcg / g) slightly higher. In the biomass of K.prostrata and Ch.glaucumplants, the amount of the U element is close to the amount of the element in the soil composition, i.e., 1.5 (2.71 mcg / g) and 3 (1.4 mcg / g) times less, respectively nevertheless, much higher relative to the biomass of plants growing in the same environment. For example, H.villosa in the plant is 0.216 mcg / g, in A.diffusa- 0.161 mcg / g, in A.pseudalhagi- 0.851 mcg / g, in Astragalus - 0.944 mcg / g in F.foetida- 0.836 mcg / g, in the composition of A.albidum- 0.69 mcg /

andinI.songarica- 0.12mcg / g.It was found that the amount of Ce element in the composition of the plantC.physodes is 51.8 mcg / g and in the composition of K.prostrata48.9 mcg / g, i.e.,it is relatively close to the number of element in the soil. Conversely, the amount of element in the H.villosaplant is 1.11 mcg/g, in the composition of Ch.glaucum-3.92 mcg / g, in the composition of A.diffusa1.83 mcg / g, in the composition of A.pseudalhagi11.3 mcg / g., in Astragalus - 11.8 mcg / g, in F.foetida18.8 mcg /g, in A. Albidum8.8 mcg / g, in T.lechmanniana4.3 mcg / g and in thecomposition of I.songarica0.55 mcg /g.When analyzing the content of the Tb element in the biomass of plants, a repetition of the situation was observed in the analysis of the Sm element. According to the indicators of assimilation of the Tb element in the biomass of K.prostrataand C.physodesplants, the content is very close to the content of this element in the soil, i.e., 0.633 mcg / g and 0.554 mcg / g, respectively, in the biomass of other plants growing in the same environment, thecontent of the element Tb is significantly low. For example, it was found that the content of the Tb element is: in the H.villosaplant, 0.0155 mcg /; in the plant Ch.glaucum- 0.0641 mcg / g; in the plant A.diffusa- 0.0209 mcg / g; in the plant A.pseudalhagi- 0.133 mcg / g; in theplant Astragalus - 0.153 mcg / g; in the plant F.foetida- 0.223 mcg / g; in the plantA. albidum, 0.092 mcg / g; in the plant T.lechmanniana- 0.046 mcg /g; in theI.songaricaplant, 0.0066 mcg / g.Also, with the above plant species, an analysis was carried out for thecontent and indicators of assimilation of the Th. So, if in the biomass ofC.physodesplants (8.04 mcg / g) and K.prostrataplant (7.9 mcg / g) the content ofthe Th element is higher relative to its content in the soil, then in the biomass ofother plants growing in this environment show very low rates.For example, it was found that the content of the Th element is: in theH.villosaplant — 0.165 mcg /; in the plant Ch.glaucum- 0.65 mcg / g; in the plantA.diffusa- 0.315 mcg / g; in the plant A.pseudalhagi- 1.92 mcg / g; in the plantAstragalus - 2.15 mcg / g; in the plant F.foetida-3.24 mcg / g; in the plant A.albidum- 1.2 mcg / g; in the plant T.

lechmanniana-0.49 mcg / g; in the plant I. songarica- 0.090 mcg/g. It can be seen from the results of the analyzes that not all plants growing in the same medium equally absorb radioactive elements. For example, C. physodes and K. prostrata have high digestibility of the Sm element from the above plants, respectively, H. villosa and I. Songarica plants have low indices. It is also possible to determine the content of radioactive elements in the soil based on the number of individuals of the plant population distributed in this environment. For example, in a certain area, H. villosa and I. songarica plants are more common than C. physodes and K. prostrata. Studies on the landscape of the Central KyzylKum with coordinates 40,031` north latitude and 60,00` east longitude with the dominant species prevailing. The above plants showed that the plants are tolerant to radioactive metals. However, not all plants absorb radioactive metals equally. Biogenic migration in plants of all species does not proceed equally. Preservation of the ability of plants to grow and take root in contaminated soils is associated with the control of harmful elements in organisms. Most plants practically do not absorb harmful elements; they can be absorbed only as part of combined complexes. In such cases, in the stems of plants such elements are concentrated in very small quantities. Plants of some other species, on the contrary, in the process of assimilation of nutrients assimilate elements almost identically and concentrate elements foreign to the body in the body. The more progressive and prolonged the vegetation period is the metabolism in plants, the more substances foreign to the body accumulate in them. We affirm our opinion through the following diagram. (chart 1)

1 - chart

When comparing the indicators of assimilation of radioactive metals by plants through the diagram, the difference in these indicators is clearly traced. So, from the above 11 plant species, *C.physodes*, *K.prostrata*, and *T. lechmanniana* have well absorbed radioactive metals. Of particular note are plants such as *C.physodes* and *K.prostrata*, which have mastered a large number of radioactive soil elements or have an equal content of these elements in their composition, as well as in the soil. An analysis of the Tulip plant showed that it only absorbed U in its biomass of radioactive elements 2 times more than they are in the soil. The remaining 4 elements relative to their content in the soil, this plant has mastered 12-15 times less. Other plant species, although they show their tolerance in these elements, nevertheless they practically did not master them from the composition of the soil. For example, plants such as *H.villosa*, *A.diffusa*, and *I.songarica* practically did not absorb the radioactive elements. From the obtained plant indicators, the following conclusions can be drawn: Plant species such as *C.physodes*, *K.prostrata*, and *T. lechmanniana*, which served as the object of study, are considered to be plants that absorb radioactive elements very well. The assimilation of a large number of certain

radioactive elements by one plant species creates an obstacle to the assimilation of a large number of other radioactive elements, and this clearly shows that one plant species has hyperaccumulation properties for the assimilation of just one element. If plants assimilate radioactive elements in an amount equal to or close to their content in the soil, then these plants show accumulative properties with respect to all radioactive elements contained in the soil; The above plants *C. physodes*, *K. prostrata* and *T. lechmanniana* can be used for mass reproduction in order to recultivate infected soils. Pollution of the atmosphere, soil, water and food by radioactive elements is not only a threat to living organisms, but also threatens their future. The practical implementation of the results of our research is important in reducing the excess migration of radioactive metals in the biosphere and preventing existing problems with emerging modern environmental problems.

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